
5G EVE

5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials

Deliverable D6.5

**Standards monitoring and adoption report
and final impact assessment report**

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
5G IA	5G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
B5G	Beyond 5G
B5G-app	Beyond 5G application
CCNC	Consumer Communications & Networking Conference
CES	Consumer Technology Association Event
DoA	Declaration of Activities
ENI	Experiential Networked Intelligence
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standard Institute
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
ICC	International Conference on Communications
ISG	Industry Standard Group and International Stakeholders Group
MEC	MultiAccess Edge Computing
OSM	OpenSource MANO
R&D	Research & Development
SDO	Standards Development Organization
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
TMV	Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable presents an overview of the activities carried out by the 5G EVE project referred to standardization as well as provides an assessment of the overall impact generated by the project.

Both kind of activities reflect the relation of the project with external stakeholders and the way in which the project influences the industry as well as the way in which the project gets influenced by the industry.

Standardization has a clear impact on transfer to the industry. It is the privileged vehicle for transferring to the industry whatever advance beyond the state of the art, settling the basis for new developments, complementing current solutions or improvements of them. In this sense 5G EVE has contributed to the industry from two main perspectives: (1) the experimental one, by contributing on methodologies and testing approaches; and (2) the technological one, by moving into the industry novelties developed as part of the development of the 5G EVE platform itself, which has faced a number of challenges not previously met.

Of course, the project has been influenced as well by the latest developments coming from standardization by incorporating new technologies on the platform in order to represent an up-to-date experimental environment for verticals. This flexibility of incorporating technologies is an important result as well, since reflects the flexibility of the platform.

Furthermore, more generic dissemination activities are also detailed in this deliverable, more focused on generic societal impact addressing wider audiences. This deliverable presents a summary of the impacts achieved in this direction, echoing the importance and the relevant contributions of the project at large.

1 Introduction

This deliverable reports the activities related to standardization carried out during the lifetime of the 5G EVE project, as well as some actions that will continue after the project end.

Standardization was recognized as a key aspect to address even from the inception of the 5G EVE project. Along the project execution period, a number of contributions have been provided to different standardization fora on specific topics in relation with the novelties explored and developed within the project.

5G EVE, as an experimental facility for 5G verticals, was conceived with the idea of integrating multiple and diverse network technologies, including RAN, Core, Transport and edge computing capabilities, all of them constituting realistic end-to-end environments where testing advanced 5G-based vertical services. Because of the multi-site nature of the project, the resulting experimental facility is formed by an interconnection and integration of multiple administrative domains.

The technologies considered by 5G EVE have been evolving during the time of the project. In consequence, 5G EVE has also evolved the overall platform by incorporating the latest advances available, allowing to perform experiments with the more recent solutions for a prompt experience from verticals.

The complexity in the interplay of technologies for experimenting 5G services, including the multi-site interworking, predicted an important influence on standards. 5G EVE has certainly confirmed such prediction by producing relevant contributions and triggering the development of new standardization activities. This document summarizes work done and the interaction with different Standard Development Organizations (SDOs).

1.1 Objectives

5G EVE was defined with a clear goal on standardization, including the consideration of a specific project task for that purpose (resulting in the establishment of Task 6.2). This activity was perceived from the beginning as a bidirectional action, in the sense that any progress on the standardization arena would influence the evolution of 5G EVE as experimental infrastructure, but also in the sense that any progress beyond of the state of the art derived from the project could be contributed to the relevant SDO in each particular area.

This deliverable addresses the objectives established for Task 6.2, as follows:

1. Identify target SDOs where to contribute relevant project outcomes.
2. Submit contributions to selected SDOs from the different dimensions of the project for enhancing or covering technical gaps on existing state-of-the-art technologies.
3. Bring back into the project advancements and progression of standards used in the project.
4. Positioning of project developments and/or platform as pieces for further standards validation and assessment purposes, including proofs of concept and interoperability tests.
5. Produce an inventory of 5G EVE contributions.
6. Serve as basis for dissemination material of the project.

A summary of all the activities performed is provided in the following sections with a rationale on the motivation for each specific action in the overall strategy of 5G EVE to address the impact on standardization.

1.2 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows. Chapter 2 describes the methodology that the project puts in place for determining the main Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) where to concentrate the standardization activity. Chapter 3 reports the standardization contributions originated from the project, describing the specific action and the purpose of each particular contribution in relation with 5G EVE. In chapter 4 it is covered the way in which the feedback from standardization activities has been addressed within the project. Chapter 5

summarizes how the standardization work in 5G EVE has contributed to dissemination of the project activities. As prospection of the project influence in the next future, chapter 6 provides an overview of the expected impact of 5G EVE after its end. Finally, chapter 7 provides concluding remarks of the deliverable.

2 Standards-related goals of 5G EVE

The 5G EVE project had a clear mission on moving into standardization arena the technical progress derived from its execution. However, planning standardization is a difficult task in the sense that new bodies may appear, the ideas from the beginning can change along the project lifetime, new technologies or industrial initiatives could emerge, etc. Also, it should be noted that the usual timing process for standardization is long, taking several years from the proposition of novel ideas up to the consolidation of them in the form of an official standard specification.

During the development of the standardization activities, it has resulted of interest the collaboration with other 5G-PPP H2020 projects [1] by working together in common contributions, strengthening the impact and widening the scope of particular contributions. The synergy among projects is quite relevant on standardization arena since permits to address a given topic from complementary angles, thus making it more generic and comprehensive.

This section reports the approach followed and how this approach has evolved along the lifetime of the project for a more effective impact on standardization, providing a consistent transfer to the industry.

2.1 Risks on the standardization process

Several are the risks related to the standardization activity. Here we summarize the main ones that have been faced by the 5G EVE project.

- **SDO fragmentation.** The standardization ecosystem is characterized by a very large fragmentation, including standardization organizations, industrial alliances, open source initiatives, etc. This is due to several reasons. One obvious is the geographical one, where in some cases regional standardization bodies with the same or similar focus emerge. In other cases, the fragmentation is motivated by the technical focus of the specific body, addressing a single number of technologies or technical areas of competence. Finally, distinct industrial interests motivate in some cases overlapped or competing approaches for the same problem space, generating situations of divergence across the industry.

In the case of 5G EVE the fragmentation has been also an issue from the perspective of the diverse set of technologies involved in the project. Even the general concept is around 5G, a variety of other technologies and tools have been necessary for building each of the particular sites, as reflected on WP2 deliverables. Technologies related to edge and cloud, transport, radio functional splits, etc, can also disperse the effort with the risk of a non-effective standardization action from the project perspective.

- **COVID-19.** The unfortunate COVID-19 pandemic impacted also the standardisation process. All SDOs (including 3GPP, ETSI, IETF, ITU-T, etc.) have had to reschedule meetings, taking them online in the majority of the cases. Although this way of working is valid, a certain slowdown of standardisation activity has been observed from the beginning of 2020.

In order to deal with these risks, Task 6.2 has performed different actions. First, in order to focus the activity and avoid dispersion, a continuous work for internal scouting has been done in key outcomes, which could represent real innovations on the specific aspects addressed in the project, then concentrating on them for having a more effective standardization action. This implied to combine the actions from internal partners as well as interact with other projects, working in a coordinated and collaborative manner.

Second, despite the slowdown on standardization activities during the more severe pandemic period, Task 6.2 has continued pursuing contributions and actions, being the more significant one the activity carried out with the proposition and development of two specific work items in ETSI INT [2], as described later on.

2.2 Project approach to standardization

The standardisation goals of the project were based on the ambition of setting up a number of complete 5G end-to-end facilities enabling an experimental experience for verticals with access to all the envisaged 5G technologies. This includes 5G new radio (5G-NR), MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing), backhaul transport technologies, core and service platforms (either physical or virtualized), slicing and orchestration capabilities, etc. Important to remark, the multi-site nature of 5G EVE allows experimentation across sites, constituting a multi-domain environment composed by different, autonomous administrative domains.

5G EVE has intended to be compliant with the latest standards available in the field of 5G, gradually adding new capabilities as soon as available from the project partners, as widely reported in WP2 deliverables. The strength of 5G EVE as an end-to-end facility is twofold. On one hand, such strength is reflected in the capability of validating vertical services and methodologies. On the other hand, the possibility of early verifying the interoperability of 5G products and services according to the latest standards by running real experiments with real users. These two kinds of actions over the same environment have allowed retro-fitting SDOs with realistic experiences and results.

At the time of project conception, a tentative area for contribution to SDOs was the idea of providing novel solutions on 5G technologies. This original idea changed during project lifetime for a number of reasons.

First, 5G EVE, as compendium of testing facilities, has been incorporating novel technologies from the partners in the consortium once these technologies were available into the market (or in an early stage close to general availability), then behaving as a “consumer” of those technologies and not as a “creator” of technologies. This implies that as much, the 5G-VE facilities could provide feedback on the technologies rather than designing novel ones. In addition to that, meaningful feedback could also be provided by the end of the project, once the experimental platform and the pilots could become fully integrated and operational.

Second, the actual novelties developed in the framework of the project has been related to the definition, developing and implementation of the 5G EVE platform itself. The specific particularities of the experimental environment, requiring the smooth integration of very diverse technologies, the multi-site nature of the overall facility, or the way in which expose testing capabilities for allowing verticals to express their needs, have all provided the ground for fostering developments beyond state of the art. Interesting to say, many of the developments associated to the 5G EVE platform come from SMEs not involved in standardization activities, thus creating an opportunity from the project in order to gain visibility and outreach with the assistance of other partners much more involved in such tasks.

As result, the project focused the standardization activity on the more impactful outcomes from the project perspective, then acting on two main directions: (1) the activities related to the experimental procedures, by contributing on methodologies and testing approaches; and (2) the activities related to technology development, centered around the novelties developed as part of the development of the 5G EVE platform itself.

2.3 Methodology

As first step, the project worked in the identification of internal strengths for accomplishing the standardization task in a realistic manner. Clearly, the 5G EVE project action leverages on the involvement of its industrial partners in relevant standardisation bodies to maximize its standardisation impact. In activities like standardization is essential the coordination of actions and contributions among partners (as indicated before, this was later extended to the coordination with other projects).

5G EVE brought together a strong and comprehensive industrial consortium with vast experience in standardisation, product implementation and benchmarking. Also, the presence of verticals in the consortium, as well as the late interaction with vertical-oriented projects (e.g., ICT-19 projects), has facilitated the convergence between vertical industries needs and the design and experimentation of innovative 5G services.

The methodology followed was the following:

- Identify how to contribute to SDOs:

- Identify the internal capabilities for driving contributions in targeted SDOs, as well as leveraging on partners' capabilities where no internal capabilities are available;
- Interact and collaborate with other projects for consolidate common contributions.
- Identify technical areas of contribution. For this, a number of actions were accomplished:
 - Identify target SDOs in line with project proposal and expectations;
 - Refine the set of SDOs identified according to 5G EVE progress and execution.

The next sections detail the process followed by this methodology.

2.3.1 Internal capabilities for contribution to standards

In order to make clearer the potential perimeter of the project at the initial stage, an SDO matrix was created (see Table 1) in order to understand what the actual reach could be according to partners' interests and capabilities.

Table 1: 5G EVE SDO matrix

SDO Body	WG	Operators			Manufacturers		SMEs	
		TIM	ORANGE	TID	ERICC	NOK	NXW	TELCA
ETSI	NFV	IC	DC	DC	IC	M	IC	
	MEC	IC		DC		M	IC	
	OSM			IC		M	DC	M
	ZSM	IC		IC	IC		M	
	ENI	IC		M				
ITU-T	IMT-2020		M		IC	M		
	SG12			M	IC	DC		
	SG13	DC	DC	M	IC			
	SG15			DC	IC			
	FG-2030			DC				
IETF	TEAS			DC	M		M	
	CCAMP			IC	IC			
	SFC			IC	IC		M	
	QUIC	IC			IC			
	IPPM	IC			IC			
	MPLS			DC	IC			
	ALTO			M	IC			
	LSR			DC	M			
	PIM			DC	IC			
	...							
IRTF	NMRG			M			M	
	NFVRG			DC			DC	
ONF	TAPI			IC	M			
	CORD				IC			
ORAN			DC	M	IC			
OAI			DC					
ONAP		IC	DC		IC			
TMForum		IC		M	M	M		
3GPP	SA2	IC		IC	IC			
	SA5	IC		IC	IC			
MEF	LSO			M	M			
NGMN	...	IC	DC		M			
GSMA	...			DC	IC			
BBF	...				IC			
LFN	OPNFV	IC	M		IC		M	
ODL			M		IC		M	
OpenStack			IC		IC		M	
ONOS					M			M

Table 1 shows the involvement declared at the beginning of the project by the industrial partners in the consortium being active on standardization matters. The legend of the table is as follows:

- DC stands for Direct Contribution, which reflects the possibility of actively contributing results from 5G EVE to a given working group through participants in the project.
- IC that stands for Indirect Contribution, which reflects the possibility of influencing contributions with results from 5G EVE through representatives from a consortium partner, but who are not participating directly in the project.
- M standing for Monitoring, which implies a follow up of the activities of the SDO/WG and potential capability of contributing results from 5G EVE.

2.3.2 Targeted standardization bodies and standards-related organizations

The 5G EVE project, once started, developed an internal exercise for identifying standardization bodies of interest, including prioritization among them, since the fragmentation on SDOs force a rationalization of the effort.

Three initial clusters of key standardization groups were identified, as follows:

- Cluster 1 – 3GPP [3], ETSI NFV [4], IETF/IRTF [5]:
The activities in this cluster with relevance to 5G EVE included architectural work identifying and functional requirements for new components and interfaces needed for enabling multi-domain services. These SDOs counted with direct support from active participants in 5G EVE project.
- Cluster 2 – ETSI MEC [6], TMForum [7], MEF, ITU-T [8]:
The activities in this cluster with relevance to 5G EVE included the specification of interfaces for supporting multi-domain services. The SDOs in this cluster counted with indirect support from the project.
- Cluster 3 – BBF [9], NGMN [10], ETSI OSM [11], ETSI ZSM [12], ONF [13]:
The activities in this cluster were limited to the monitoring on the progress of the standards there elaborated in relation with 5G, and how they could relate to or influence 5G EVE. The expectation was to define specific actions in case 5G EVE could influence such progress with outcomes from the project.

These clusters were created on the initial steps of the project. However, the subsequent action on standardization evolved by not strictly following the identified clusters for several reasons.

One primary reason was the development and execution of the project in its own. As long as the project run it became clear that the more powerful source of influence in standards could come from the development of the experimental facility itself, including the testing methodologies and definitions, rather than a simple assessment and/or interoperability of technologies. That is, the focus has been finally on the novel artefacts for experimentation being developed in the project, and the actual necessity of the vertical customers for experimentation before going commercial.

A second important reason was the evolution of the proper SDOs themselves, since they evolve on scope along the time in some cases, including the formation of new SDOs or working groups within. One clear example of this could be for instance the emergency ORAN [14] as SDO for specification of interoperable radio functional splits. Also, the evolution on the interests of the companies in the consortium with respect to the SDOs, who evolves according to the particular business strategy.

The changes on the SDOs addressed is later reflected in this deliverable in the summary of contributions performed. In the second period of the project a new clustering was established taking into account all the aforementioned aspects.

- Cluster 1 – ETSI INT [2], 3GPP [3], IETF/IRTF [4]:
The activities in this cluster consider the major outcomes from 5G EVE including architectural work and the definition of generic testing and validation framework for verticals.

- Cluster 2 –ETSI ENI [5], ETSI OSM [6], ETSI ZSM [7], ITU-T [8], ORAN [9]:

The activities in this cluster consider complementary aspects related to 5G EVE also in the direction of architecture and testing framework.

- Cluster 3 – BBF [10], NGMN [11], ETSI MEC [12], TMForum [13], MEF [18], GSMA [19], ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC41 [20], ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC42 [21]:

The activities in this cluster were essentially devoted to monitoring of the progress of the related SDOs. Even some activities could be related to 5G EVE actions in this cluster were minimized for avoiding dispersion on the standardization effort.

As a preliminary summary of the SDOs where 5G EVE has contributed (with different intensity), what is mentioned in Table 2 applies:

Table 2: Summary of contributions of 5G EVE to SDOs

SDO	Relation with 5G EVE	Action from 5G EVE
ETSI INT [2]	Testing methodologies and specifications followed in 5G EVE	Contribution to specification and rapporteur-ship of it
ETSI ENI [15]	Optimization based on AI mechanisms	Proof of concept
ETSI MEC [6]	Usage of ETSI MEC in several 5G EVE sites	Organization of plenary meeting and hackathon
ETSI ZSM [12]	Zero touch provisioning of experiments	Contribution to specification
ETSI OSM [11]	Usage of OSM as MANO stack in several 5G EVE sites	Organization of hackathon
3GPP SA5 [22]	Architectural aspects involving verticals (e.g., Non-Public Networks, NPN)	Contribution to specification
IETF BMWG [23]	Benchmarking of transport technologies	Contribution with individual draft
IRTF NMRG [24]	Intent-based slice service requests	Contribution with individual draft
ORAN [14]	Usage of functional splits in 5G EVE as well as fronthaul/backhaul transport technologies	Organization of plenary meeting and contribution to specifications
ITU-T Net2030 [25]	Evolution of testing facilities for experimentation of novel vertical services	Contribution and participation in workshop
GSMA [19]	Definition of new APIs for MEC environments	Contribution to specification

Detailed contributions are described in next chapter.

3 Standardization contributions: from 5G EVE to outside world

5G EVE has been active in standardisation activities by concentrating on the novelties that have been identified at the time of developing the experimental platform. Aspects such as orchestration of experiments, integration of vertical networks with operators' networks, testing and benchmarking methodology and specification for vertical services, interworking of the overall multisite testing platform, etc., are part of the topics on which the standardization contributions from 5G EVE have been structured. Thus, as reported in this chapter, principal contributions have been at both the conceptual level (for 5G systems) and the architectural level (for specific mechanisms incorporated into 5G EVE).

It can be highlighted that many of the novel aspects brought into standardization have been produced and led by the SMEs in the project, which originally were not intended to contribute to standardisation activities. This means that, through collaboration with other partners in the project having closer connection to standardisation, some of these institutions have gained presence, visibility and outreach.

3.1 Performed activities

In this section a description of the main standardization actions contributed by 5G EVE is presented.

3.1.1 ETSI INT [2]

The ETSI Technical committee on Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT) is focused on developing specifications to test interoperability, conformance, performance and security, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ETSI INT [2] overview

Action	Promotion of two Work Items (WIs): WI-1 on “Methodologies for E2E Testing & Validation of Vertical Applications over 5G&Beyond networks”, and WI-2 on “Specifications for E2E Testing & Validation of Vertical Applications over 5G&Beyond networks”. Several contributions and rapporteur-ship for the Technical Report (TR) associated to WI-1.
Reference	ETSI TR 103 761 [26]
Purpose	The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes. An overview presentation to ETSI INT with specific actions is expected for the next ETSI INT plenary, in June. The main contributors to this work are TIM, WINGS, and TID – all on behalf of 5G EVE project.
5G EVE Partners	ERI, TIM, WINGS, TELCA, TID, NOK
Collaborating projects	5G-VINNI, 5GENESIS, 5GROWTH

This initiative can be considered as the flagship contribution from 5G EVE to standardization. For that reason, Section 3.2 is devoted to a deeper insight on this particular case.

3.1.2 ETSI ENI [15]

The ETSI Industry Specification Group on Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) pursues the definition of a Cognitive Network Management architecture leveraging on Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques together with context-aware policies. The objective is to permit the adaptation of services according to changes in user needs, environmental conditions, business goals, etc. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ETSI ENI is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ETSI ENI [15] overview

Action	Proof of concept (PoC) 09 “Autonomous Network Slice Management for 5G Vertical Services”
Reference	https://eniwiki.etsi.org/index.php?title=Poc_09:_Autonomous_Network_Slice_Management_for_5G_Vertical_Services Approved final report: https://eniwiki.etsi.org/images/2/27/ENI%2821%29000010_POC_9_Final_Report.pdf
Purpose	<p>The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to management and orchestration.</p> <p>The PoC has been articulated around the autonomous network slice management for 5G vertical services. It leverages on the usage of artificial intelligent techniques for both to Vertical Service and Network Slice Management functions, enabling autonomous behaviour.</p> <p>This PoC also included the integration with ETSI OSM and a public virtual demonstration has been held during the OSM Ecosystem Day, on March 2021 (ref. http://osm-download.etsi.org/ftp/osm-9.0-nine/OSM-MR10-hackfest/EcosystemDay/OSM-MR10%20ED5%20-%20Nextworks.pdf).</p>
5G EVE Partners	NXW, UC3M, TIM, WINGS
Collaborating projects	5GROWTH, 5G-TOURS

3.1.3 ETSI ZSM [12]

The ETSI Industry Specification Group on Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM) is centred on the full end-to-end automation of network and service management, with the objective of enabling autonomous networks driven by high-level policies and rules (e.g., making possible aspects such as self-configuration, self-healing, self-optimization, etc). An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ETSI ZSM is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ETSI ZSM [12] overview

Action	Contribution for the technical specification ZSM 003 on management and orchestration of network slicing.
Reference	Contribution ZSM(19)000488 (Note: there is no public link to this document)
Purpose	<p>The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to management and orchestration.</p> <p>Contribution focused on the management exposure interfaces offered to vertical customers for the end to end management and orchestration of network slicing. It proposed the usage of the GSMA Generic Slice Template for Network Slice [27] as a Service (NSaaS) scenarios. This is relevant from the perspective of how vertical services (and by extension, the associated experiments) are requested.</p> <p>The document was accepted.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	5G-VINNI

3.1.4 ETSI OSM [11]

The ETSI Open Source Management and Orchestration (MANO) (OSM) represents an open source initiative aligned with ETSI NFV stack developments, constituting a reference implementation of NFV MANO. The OSM code is provided under the Apache Public License 2.0. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ETSI OSM [11] is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: ETSI OSM [11] overview

Action	8th OSM Hackfest and co-located 5G Day (Lucca, Italy)
Reference	https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/8th_OSM_Hackfest http://osm-download.etsi.org/ftp/osm-6.0-six/8th-hackfest/5Gday/5GEVE_OSM_hackfest_CNIT%20v2.pdf
Purpose	Through this action it was reported the contribution of 5G EVE related to multi-site management and orchestration in the usage of OSM. The OSM Hackfest took place in November 2019. The multi-site approach involves the design of a specific interworking layer, as developed by WP3. There is an interaction among local NFV Orchestrator and this interworking layer that requires translation of descriptors and adaptation on the API methods, as well as novel concepts such as multi-site catalogue.
5G EVE Partners	CNIT
Collaborating projects	5GCity, MATILDA, 5GMEDIA

3.1.5 3GPP SA5 [22]

The 3GPP System Aspects Working Group 5 (SA5) is in charge of developing the management, orchestration and charging specification for 3GPP [3] systems, from functional and service perspectives. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in 3GPP SA5 [22] is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: 3GPP SA5 [3] overview

Action	Contributions to Release 16 of 3GPP [3]
Reference	Contributions S5-196748 [28], S5-196734 [29], S5-201596 [30], S5-202331 [31]
Purpose	The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to architecture aspects as well as management and orchestration. Specifically, the topics addressed have been: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The introduction of a new use case for the deployment of a stand-alone non-public network (NPN) with 3GPP and non-3GPP segments - S5-196734 [29], as contribution to TR 28.807 [32] • A contribution to the definition of the management service in charge of creating, terminating, and querying KPI jobs - S5-196748 [28], as change request to TS 28.550 [33]. • Clarification of the definition of the tenant concept - S5-202331 [31], as change request to TS 28.533 [34]. • Clarifications on network slice as a service (NSaaS) in the management of public-network-integrated NPN - S5-201596 [30], as contribution to TR 28.807 [32]

	<p>All of them became accepted Tdocs.</p> <p>The contributions are relevant from the architectural perspective for vertical-specific customers as consumers of network capabilities targeting 5G EVE objectives.</p> <p>The first three are joint contributions from 5G-VINNI, while the fourth is a joint contribution from 5G-VINNI and 5GROWTH. Partners in EVE contributing to this are TID for all of them, including ORANGE in the latest one.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TID (S5-196748 [28], S5-196734 [29], S5-202331 [31]) TID, ORA (S5-201596 [30])
Collaborating projects	5G-VINNI (S5-196748 [28], S5-196734 [29], S5-202331 [31]) 5G-VINNI, 5GROWTH (S5-201596 [30])

3.1.6 IETF BMWG [5]

The IETF Benchmarking Methodology Working Group (BMWG) produces recommendations relevant to the performance of internetworking IETF-related technologies, including benchmarks for network devices, systems, and services. The scope of work includes benchmarks for the management, control, and forwarding planes. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in IETF BMWG [5] is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: IETF BMWG [5] overview

Action	5G transport network benchmarking draft proposal
Reference	draft-contreras-bmwg-5g [35]
Purpose	<p>The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to testing methodologies and specifications.</p> <p>The purpose of this contribution is to overview the implications of 5G services in transport networks, providing guidance on benchmarking of the infrastructures supporting those services.</p> <p>The aspects to consider are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data-plane benchmarking, which refers to both hardware capabilities and encapsulation protocols • Control-plane benchmarking, which relates to the programmability of the network • Management-plane benchmarking, which is associated with the management of the lifecycle of the slice/service • Architecture benchmarking, which relates to the overall end-to-end solution <p>This is a work-in-progress.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	5GENESIS

3.1.7 IRTF NMRG [24]

The IRTF Network Management Research Group (NMRG) explores new technologies for the management of the Internet technologies. A specific line of work is on intent-based systems. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in IRTF NMRG [24] is presented in Table 9.

Table 9: IRTF NMRG [24] overview

Action	Contribution of an individual draft focused on intent-based mechanisms for transport slicing
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Reference	draft-contreras-nmrg-transport-slice-intent [36]
Purpose	<p>The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to architecture aspects as well as management and orchestration.</p> <p>This document explores the usage of intent technologies for requesting network slices, especially for IETF-related technologies (i.e., transport networks).</p> <p>This contribution builds on the generic intent-based mechanisms developed in 5G EVE narrowing down the scope to deal with the specific case of the invocation of slices in the transport network, which can be seen as a subset of the original scope.</p> <p>This is a work-in-progress.</p>
5G EVE Partners	WINGS, TID
Collaborating projects	--

3.1.8 ORAN [14]

The O-RAN Alliance is working on the full definition of interoperable radio functional splits, including its control and orchestration, the virtualization of the different components, and the testing of multi-vendor implementations. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ORAN is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: ORAN [14] overview

Action	Contribution to ORAN specifications relative to Xhaul transport networks (ORAN working group 9)
Reference	<p>O-RAN.WG9.XPSAAS - O-RAN Xhaul Packet Switched Architectures and Solutions</p> <p>O-RAN.WG9.XTRP-TST - Xhaul Transport Testing</p> <p>(Note: there are no public links to these documents)</p>
Purpose	<p>The main purposes of this action were to position the project platform as a valuable piece for O-RAN validation as well as contribute relevant project outcomes, related to testing methodologies and specifications.</p> <p>Radio functional splits impose very stringent requirements to the transport networks, in order to address fronthaul, midhaul and backhaul network segments. This work first specifies viable solutions for transport of those network segments, for later on specify the testing methodology and specifications to validate these solutions. The overall techniques and testing defined influence verticals' architectural decisions especially when introducing radio functional split solutions in NPNs (or in the interconnection with operators' networks).</p>
5G EVE Partners	<p>TID (O-RAN.WG9.XPSAAS)</p> <p>ORA, TID (O-RAN.WG9.XTRP-TST)</p>
Collaborating projects	--

3.1.9 ITU-T Net2030 [25]

The ITU-T Focus Group on Network 2030 was setup for prospect the necessary capabilities of networks for the year 2030 and beyond, when it will be required to support novel scenarios, such as holographic type communications, extremely fast response in critical situations and high-precision communication demands of emerging market verticals. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ITU-T [8] is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: ITU-T Net2030 [25] overview

Action	Contribution to Network 2030 Architecture Framework
Reference	Contribution NET2030-I-120 [25]
Purpose	<p>The main purposes of this action were the positioning the 5G EVE platform and the dissemination of the project. In addition to that, it was also reported the contribution of 5G EVE focused on testing facilities for 5G and beyond 5G.</p> <p>5G EVE has contributed by providing a view of the need to leverage testing facilities, such as the one in the project for assessing the new services proposed in the Network 2030 Focus Group.</p> <p>The contribution was noted since testing was not initially under the scope of the focus group.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	--

3.1.10 GSMA [19]

The GSMA is an industrial association grouping the majority of mobile operators. The GSMA [19] produces a number of studies and analysis that serve as basis for specific development of standards in SDOs focused on the topic of interest. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in GSMA [19] is presented in Table 12.

Table 12: GSMA [19] overview

Action	Contribution to IG.08 “Multi-access Edge Computing API Analysis”
Reference	No public reference (confidential document)
Purpose	<p>The main purpose of this action was the contribution of relevant project outcomes, related to multi-site integration of compute and virtualized environments.</p> <p>The document performs a gap analysis on MEC APIs proposing directions in terms of operational, business, management, policy and slicing APIs. Part of the proposed APIs is related to architectural scenarios such as the multi-site one in 5G EVE.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TIM, TID
Collaborating projects	--

3.2 Detailed overview of contribution to ETSI INT [2]

The execution of the 5G EVE project made clear the need for vertical industries to experiment and pilot their “5G enabled” business case before moving to commercial stage. A clear advantage for all the stakeholders in 5G business is the definition of a common, generic 5G and beyond application testing and validation framework which validates the vertical application or service in a systematic manner under different 5G technology choices and deployment environments. The objective is also to get the vertical involved in the design and result evaluation phase, which goes beyond current network testing paradigm of service providers.

With this need in mind, 5G EVE project decided to launch an initiative for standardizing such a generic framework, producing recommendations on such validation framework and methodologies, and leveraging the experience from EU 5G PPP [1] trial projects.

In this direction, 5G EVE took the initiative of proposing two specific work items.

- WI-1 on “Methodologies for E2E Testing & Validation of Vertical Applications over 5G & Beyond networks”. The goal of the work item is to survey and review the existing methodologies for Testing and Validation of vertical applications designed for leveraging the potential of 5G & Beyond networks, in order to identify existing gaps in such methodologies and propose solutions to cover them. The methodology describes a Reference Testing & Validation Process, as well as Architecture, Point of Control and Observations, KPI validation strategies and mechanisms, and other aspects involved in the testing and validation of innovative vertical applications enabled by 5G & Beyond networks. The scope of analysis takes into consideration the vision, requirements, architectures and novel use cases of the 5G ecosystem.
- WI-2 on “Specifications for E2E Testing & Validation of Vertical Applications over 5G & beyond networks”. The goal of this work item is to develop general Test & Validation Specifications applicable to the widest range possible of vertical applications created for leveraging the potential of 5G & Beyond networks. The Specifications to be developed, therefore, are expected to: (i) cater for general Test & Validation needs for 5G-enabled vertical applications; (ii) build upon relevant specifications for the underlying network system, mainly from 3GPP [3] (Rel.15 & Rel 16), ETSI NFV and IETF; and (iii) adopt the methodologies created by ETSI INT WI Methodologies for E2E Testing & Validation of Vertical Applications over 5G & Beyond networks. The scope of analysis takes into consideration the recurrent needs of 5G-enabled applications’ Testing & Validation strategies, which pivot around Core 5G KPIs, and 5G Network Slice Types (eMBB, URLLC, mMTC).

The 5G EVE project led the effort by involving on it the two other ICT-17 projects developing experimental facilities, that is, 5G-VINNI and 5GENESIS, in order to provide a comprehensive approach to the topic, complementing the individual progress carried out and lessons learned on these three projects. Finally, also contributions from 5GROWTH were collected, thus making this effort even more comprehensive.

The development of the first WI started in H2 2020 and is expected to finish by July 2021 with the release of ETSI TR 103 761 [26], with the status of stable draft at the time of writing this deliverable. After that, the second WI will begin, leveraging on the findings of ETSI TR 103 761 [26].

The purpose of ETSI TR 103 761 [26] is to provide recommendations on methodologies for end-to-end testing and validation of vertical applications over 5G and beyond networks. The document includes recommendations covering the most aspects of a B5G-app validation framework by providing recommendation on B5G capabilities and enablers, on the testing and validation environment, on involved processes, on the relevant KPI mechanisms and, finally, on the design of vertical applications under test. Such recommendations can be equally applicable to a wide range of industry verticals, application cases and beyond 5G scenarios.

The main value of such end-to-end testing and validation activity is the fact that the vertical application provider can experiment with the 5G and beyond network in order to make business decisions previously to going into commercialization. In this context it is assumed that the subject under test is the application and that the 5G and beyond network setup (as well as the configurations considered in such experimentation) have already been tested and qualified both from functionality and performance perspective.

The technical report provides a survey and review of the existing methodologies for testing and validating vertical applications, leveraging on the experiences gain through several 5G-PPP [1] projects (namely 5G EVE, 5G-VINNI and 5GENESIS). This exercise permits the identification of existing gaps in such methodologies, proposing solutions to cover them. The proposed methodology in ETSI TR 103 761 [26] describes Process, Mechanisms and Strategies involved in the testing and validation of innovative vertical applications enabled by 5G and Beyond networks. The work does not consider any assumption on the specific business or nature of the vertical domain, with the intention to identify common methodologies applicable to as wide a range of vertical domains as possible.

From the several recommendations that will be part of the technical report, in terms of capabilities to be supported (e.g., 5G NR, edge and cloud capabilities, etc), architectural approach (multi-site environment,

capability exposure, etc), tools (for KPI collection and analysis, performance diagnostics, reporting, etc), processes (experiment requirement collection, descriptors, etc), and finally, a generic testing framework. Here, we provide as an example the proposed architecture for such a generic testing framework. Figure 1 depicts the proposed framework.

Figure 1: Generic testing framework

The testing framework should ensure that the experiment environment is properly prepared and configured to enable the experiment execution in a given timeslot and for a given configuration. As seen, the framework is aligned with 5G EVE architecture and inherits development approaches worked out in the technical work packages of the project, mainly WP3, WP4 and WP5, as described on the corresponding deliverables. Full details are provided in ETSI TR 103 761 [26], so the reader is referred to that for this framework and the many other recommendations provided there.

A summary of the approach, recommendations and conclusions of this activity has been presented in different venues:

- ITU ETSI IEEE Joint SDOs Brainstorming Workshop on Testbeds Federations for 5G & Beyond, 15 March 2021, <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/Workshops-and-Seminars/20210316/Pages/programme.aspx>
- 5G-PPP TMV Webinar, 18 Jun 2021, <https://5g-ppp.eu/event/practical-insights-from-5g-test-measurement-and-kpi-validation-with-vertical-applications/>
- 5G-PPP Pre-Standardization WG regular meeting in April.

4 Feedback on standardization: from outside world to 5G EVE

The 5G EVE project has also benefitted from the feedback provided by consortium partners, especially the industrial ones, which have brought latest technology developments to the project. This has been documented on WP2 deliverables, allowing the experimental facilities to incorporate up-to-date solutions.

Apart from that, an important flow of feedback has come from the interaction with the 5G-PPP [1] working groups' ecosystem. This interaction is reported here.

4.1 Participation in 5G-PPP pre-standardization working group

The 5G-PPP Pre-Standardization WG pursues to strength the competitiveness of European industry since standardization is often seen as a significant contributor to growth and innovation for the overall industry. The Pre-Standardization WG has supports the participating projects by keeping track of the contributed material and fostering coordination and synergies among projects.

5G EVE has participated actively in the 5G-PPP Pre-Standards working group since the starting of Task 6.2. This participation has allowed to promote and disseminate standardization outcomes of the project, socializing the project results with the rest of the 5G-PPP community.

Specifically, the contributions to IETF BMWG [5], ITU-T Network 2030 [25] and ETSI INT [2] were presented on regular meetings through dedicated sessions. Furthermore, the overall contributions were reported for the tracker setup by the working group to document the impacts on standardization from 5G-PPP [1] projects.

Complementary to that, 5G EVE has also received substantial information from the Pre-Standardization WG. This WG disseminates and coordinates different activities of interest to the projects. Apart from periodic update on SDOs progress and standards events, the WG coordinates a number of other initiatives such as a series of 5G Vertical User Workshops, with the target of supporting 5G standardization for vertical industries, of great relevance for 5G EVE.

The dissemination of all of this information has been accomplished through the project mailing list and specific reporting on 5G EVE project meetings.

4.2 5G-PPP Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation WG [37]

The 5G-PPP Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation (TMV) Working Group [37] aim is to promote a common approach among projects with focus on T&M methodologies to support 5G vertical use cases, pilots and trials. The WG concentrates on the development of Test and Measurement methods, test cases, procedures and the formalization and validation of KPIs.

5G EVE motivated the creation of this 5G-PPP WG, and has participated actively in it by taking vice-chair role since its creation (and then the chairman role in 2021). 5G EVE has contributed to the WG with presentations of testing and KPI topics, participation on workshops, and key contributions to its two white papers, namely:

- “Validating 5G Technology Performance: Assessing 5G architecture and Application Scenarios”, <https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/TMV-White-Paper-V1.1-25062019.pdf>
- “Service performance measurement methods over 5G experimental networks”, https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Service-performance-measurement-methods-over-5G-experimental-networks_08052021-Final.pdf

The approach and contents of the latest 5G-PPP TMV Whitepaper were already shared at the 5G-PPP Webinar moderated by 5G EVE (program available in <https://5g-ppp.eu/event/practical-insights-from-5g-test-measurement-and-kpi-validation-with-vertical-applications/>). This privileged channel of feedback into the project has facilitated the alignment of TMV WG activities with the ones in 5G EVE.

Last but not least, outcomes from the TMV WG [37] have fed the standardization work in ETSI INT [2], closing the virtuous loop of collaboration and synergy between projects.

4.3 SME WG [38]

The Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) Working Group [38] promotes the participation of SMEs in the 5G PPP ecosystem. Here, the participation of 5G EVE has been achieved through the analysis of SME involvement in the project.

Notably, as indicated before, the standardization effort in the project has revealed the potential of the SMEs partners to drive significant standardization contributions. Together with the other industrial partners in Task 6.2, much more involved in standardization, the SMEs have been able to get involved and transfer into SDOs relevant outcomes.

In this case, the feedback channel to the project has been the own SMEs participating in 5G EVE.

5 Input to dissemination

A complementary mission of the effort in standardization has been the positioning of the project in the standards community, providing visibility and disseminating both the generated outcomes and the project itself. This has come from the participation and/or organization of standards-related events, where 5G EVE has been promoted.

5.1 Performed activities

This section describes the main standardization actions supporting the dissemination of 5G EVE.

5.1.1 ETSI MEC [17]

The ETSI Industry Specification Group on Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) [17] works on the definition of a new ecosystem enabling the deployment and operation of edge computing capabilities supporting different applications and services, including the specification of APIs for the consumption of some of those applications at the edge. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ETSI ISG MEC and the MEC Hackathon are presented in Table 13 and Table 14, respectively.

Table 13: ETSI ISG MEC plenary meeting

Action	ETSI ISG MEC 17 th plenary meeting (Leganés, Spain)
Reference	https://portal.etsi.org/Meetings.aspx#/meeting?MtgId=35385
Purpose	<p>The main purposes of this action were to position the project platform as a valuable piece for further MEC validation and serve as basis for dissemination of the project.</p> <p>The meeting was hosted by UC3M on March 2019. A visit to the Spanish site of 5G EVE was organized in the context of the meeting, including a demo of 5G EVE's Industry 4.0 use case based on ASTI AGVs reporting a collection of KPI metrics (relevant for MEC use cases).</p>
5G EVE Partners	UC3M, ASTI
Collaborating projects	--

Table 14: MEC Hackathon

Action	MEC hackathon within the Edge Computing congress (in London, UK)
Reference	https://www.etsi.org/newsroom/press-releases/1648-2019-09-developers-at-mec-hackathons-endorsed-by-etsi-challenged-to-trial-edge-computing-for-5g-in-uk-and-china
Purpose	<p>The main purposes of this action were the positioning the 5G EVE platform and the dissemination of the project.</p> <p>The hackathon took place in September 2019, as part of the industrial event Edge Computing congress, organized by knect365 / Informa.</p> <p>The link with 5G EVE was through the sponsorship of Telefonica, since one of the prizes was the possibility of deploying a demonstrator on the edge computing facilities of the 5G EVE Spanish site.</p>

5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	--

5.1.2 ETSI OSM [11]

The ETSI Open Source Management and Orchestration (MANO) (OSM) [11] represents an open source initiative aligned with ETSI NFV stack developments, constituting a reference implementation of NFV MANO [4]. The OSM code is provided under the Apache Public License 2.0. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in the ETSI OSM Hackathon is presented in Table 15

Table 15: ETSI OSM Hackfest

Action	8th OSM Hackfest and co-located 5G Day (Lucca, Italy)
Reference	https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/8th_OSM_Hackfest
Purpose	The main purposes of this action were the positioning the 5G- EVE platform and the dissemination of the project. The participation on OSM Hackfest helped to promote 5G EVE within the OSM community for attraction of developers.
5G EVE Partners	CNIT
Collaborating projects	5GCity, MATILDA, 5GMEDIA

5.1.3 ORAN [14]

The O-RAN Alliance is working on the full definition of interoperable radio functional splits, including its control and orchestration, the virtualization of the different components, and the testing of multi-vendor implementations. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in ORAN [14] is presented in Table 16.

Table 16: ORAN work summit

Action	O-RAN work summit face to face meeting (Madrid, Spain)
Reference	https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5ad774cce74940d7115044b0/t/5c6b197171c10bf8997eb72d/1550522739267/FINAL+O-RAN+MWC2019+Release.pdf
Purpose	The main purposes of this action were to position the 5G EVE platform and serve as basis for dissemination of the project. The meeting took place in February 2019. 5G EVE was positioned as experimental platform for future 5G vertical services that could leverage on radio functional split solutions.
5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	--

5.1.4 ITU-T Net2030 [25]

The ITU-T Focus Group on Network 2030 [25] was setup for prospect the necessary capabilities of networks for the year 2030 and beyond, when it will be required to support novel scenarios, such as holographic type

communications, extremely fast response in critical situations and high-precision communication demands of emerging market verticals. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in the ITU workshop is presented in Table 17.

Table 17: ITU Workshop

Action	Sixth ITU Workshop on Network 2030 and Demo Day (Lisbon, Portugal)
Reference	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/Workshops-and-Seminars/20200113/Documents/Luis_M_Contreras.pdf
Purpose	<p>The main purposes of this action were the positioning the 5G EVE platform and the dissemination of the project.</p> <p>The workshop took place on January 2020.</p> <p>The presentation addresses the main challenges to be foreseen by operators in the evolution to 2030. One of the highlights is the need for experimental facilities such as 5G EVE.</p>
5G EVE Partners	TID
Collaborating projects	

5.1.5 ETSI INT [2]

The ETSI INT [2] activity has represented the most representative action from 5G-EVE. As reported in previous chapter, a number of dissemination activities have accompanied the development of the ETSI TR 103 761 [26]. An overview of the actions of 5G-EVE partners in the ETSI INT Brainstorming workshop is presented in Table 18.

Table 18: ETSI INT Brainstorming Workshop

Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ITU ETSI IEEE Joint SDOs Brainstorming Workshop on Testbeds Federations for 5G & Beyond, 15 March 2021, https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/Workshops-and-Seminars/20210316/Pages/programme.aspx • 5G-PPP TMV Webinar, 18 Jun 2021, https://5g-ppp.eu/event/practical-insights-from-5g-test-measurement-and-kpi-validation-with-vertical-applications/ • 5G-PPP Pre-Standardization WG regular meeting in April.
Reference	Indicated above
Purpose	The main purposes of this dissemination action has been to communicate the activity to a broader audience including diverse SDOs and 5G-PPP ecosystem
5G EVE Partners	ERI, TIM, WINGS, TELCA, TID, NOK
Collaborating projects	5G-VINNI, 5GENESIS, 5GROWTH

6 Communication and dissemination impact assessment

The communication and dissemination activities of 5G EVE have been an important element for achieving a high impact for the project results.

Throughout the project, 5G EVE successfully disseminated its results to target audiences including the 5G research community and industry in vertical sectors like energy, industry 4.0, and media. A special focus was on ICT-19 projects and other users of the 5G EVE platform. From spring 2020 to the end of the project, the COVID-19-related travel and meeting restrictions seriously affected activities through the cancellation, postponement or virtualisation of almost all major events we had targeted, including MWC [39] 2020 and 2021 as well as EuCNC [40] 2020 and 2021. 5G EVE successfully adapted its dissemination and communication activities to the new situation and created in a 2020 and 2021 a number of webinars, culminating in the Final 5G EVE Webinar on 26 May 2021, which presented all major achievements of the project.

6.1 Achieved communication and dissemination goals

The communication and dissemination activities of 5G EVE were driven by a set of goals, as outlined below.

Communication goals

- Promote the activities and results of the project in the most effective way.
- Identify and get in contact with members of relevant target audiences.
- Significantly increase awareness and comprehension among target audiences of the goals, activities and results of the project.
- Engage target audiences in a two-way exchange on the activities and results of the project and the overall 5G PPP [1] activities and results.
- Collect and utilise responses from target audiences, which could help 5G EVE improve its results and impact.

Dissemination goals

- Disclose public 5G EVE project results to relevant target audiences in order to progress their work for the advancement of technology, science, industry and society in Europe.
- Make the contents of public 5G EVE project results highly accessible for target audiences by making them easy to understand and use.
- Make target audiences interested in using the public 5G EVE project results.
- Create an active stakeholder community of target audiences with high interest in using the 5G EVE results.
- Engage with external verticals outside of the 5G PPP [1] to increase their interest in using the 5G EVE end-to-end facility.

5G EVE has fully achieved these goals, as explained in detail below.

6.2 Performed communication and dissemination activities

The first major output was the project website at <https://www.5G EVE.eu> which was launched already at the project start in July 2018. Further outputs included publications (peer-reviewed papers, project flyer, newsletter, etc.) as well as workshops, presentations at events, webinars, and demo booths. Highlights included a highly interactive networking session on 5G infrastructures at ICT 2018 in Vienna (see Figure 3) and a demonstration of the four 5G EVE site facilities at EuCNC [40] 2019 in Valencia (see Figure 2), which achieved the second-best popularity rating by the audience.

6.2.1 Milestones

Both dissemination/communication-related project milestones, MS3 and MS6, have been achieved through the organisation of two webinars and the publication of documentation on the 5G EVE E2E facility for verticals:

MS3: 5G EVE dissemination of project to ICT-19-2019/ICT-22-2018 participants (September 2018)

A 5G EVE Webinar for ICT-19/22 proposers was organized on 20 September 2018, which attracted 60 participants, mainly from verticals in ICT-19/ICT-22.

MS6: Approach ICT-19-2019/ ICT-22-2018 vertical industries with solid description of 5G E2E facility (May 2019)

Another 5G EVE Webinar was organized for ICT-19/22 projects on 9 May 2019. 100 participants, mainly from verticals in ICT-19/ICT-22, attended the webinar. A detailed description of the E2E facility was published on the 5G EVE website at <https://www.5g-eve.eu/end-to-end-facility/>.

6.2.2 Events

As outlined in the communication and dissemination plan (D6.1), 5G EVE targeted a number of major events for disseminating its results through conference presentations, workshops, and exhibitions. Especially since the start of the Covid-19 pandemic and the related travel and meeting restrictions in spring 2020, 5G EVE focused on organising webinars, in order to continue reaching its target audiences and disseminating its results.

Figure 2: EuCNC 2019 in Valencia - demos

Figure 3: ICT 2018 in Vienna – networking session

Major event participation 2018-2019: Paper presentation at 8th IEEE International Symposium on Cloud and Services Computing (IEEE SC2), Paris (19 November 2018); Presentation at FOKUS FUSECO Forum, Berlin (15 November 2018); Presentation at 5G Italy, Rome (4-12 December 2018); Paper presentation at IEEE ICC 2019 workshop: 5G-Trials – From 5G Experiments to Business Validation, Shanghai (20 May 2019); Exhibition booth, workshops and paper presentations at EuCNC 2019 (Figure 2), Valencia (18-21 June 2019), Presentation at IEEE 5G World Forum - 2nd Workshop on 5G Trials, Virtual (1 October 2019), 5G EVE demo at the ETSI IoT Week, Sophia Antipolis, 21-25 October 2019, (Figure 4), Keynote at 5G Italy 2019, Rome, Italy (3 December 2019).

Figure 4: 5G EVE team at ETSI IoT Week 2019

Major events participation 2020- 2021: Keynote at CCNC 2020, Las Vegas (12 January 2020); Demo of tourism use case at FITUR 2020 (22-24 January 2020); Poster presentation at ICIN 2020, Paris (27 February 2020); Webinar including live online demo of 5G EVE Portal (27 February 2020); NSF visit at Spanish and French site (9-12 March 2020) (see figure below); First 5G EVE Training Webinar (6 May 2020); Presentation at 5GROWTH online workshop (9 June 2020); Paper presentation at virtual EuCNC 2020 (16 June 2020); Second 5G EVE Training Webinar (23 June 2020), Greek 5G EVE Demo Webinar (7 July 2020), French 5G EVE Demo Webinar (9 July 2020), Italian 5G EVE Site Webinar (18 November 2020), 5G Trials Workshop at IEEE 5G World Forum 2020 (10 September 2020), Joint 5G EVE - 5G-TOURS Webinar (3 December 2020), First 5G EVE Learn and Drive (26 January 2021), Second 5G EVE Learn and Drive (17 March 2021), Final 5G EVE Webinar (26 May 2021), EuCNC & 6G Summit, 8-11 June 2021, (Figure 5), Tutorial - French 5G EVE Site (17 June 2021)

Figure 5: 5G EVE virtual booth at EuCNC 2021

A complete list of 5G EVE event participations is available on the project website at: <https://www.5g-eve.eu/list-of-event-participation/>

6.2.3 Publications

Online and offline publications were one of the four pillars of 5G EVE's communication and dissemination activities. All publications were aimed to achieve impacts towards the target audiences, especially verticals, and were monitored against the KPIs (see section 6.3).

- 51 scientific papers published (2018-2021)
- 2 editions of the 5G EVE project flyer published (2019 and 2020)
- 17 news items published
- 6 issues of 5G EVE newsletter "5G Infrastructure News" published from December 2019 - June 2021

6.2.4 Project Website

A preliminary version of the 5G EVE project website was launched under the domain name www.5g-eve.eu in July 2018. By the end of August 2018, the website had already reached a high level of maturity. Since then, the website has been regularly updated in the Publications, News and Events sections. The project website (see Figure 6) served as the central reference point for all of the project's communication and dissemination activities.

In order to keep the website useful and attractive for target audiences, we regularly published news items, videos and further updates. Web statistics showed that this concept worked – more than 11,000 visitors were attracted by our website, as shown in the traffic statistics depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Project website

Figure 7: Audience for the website

6.2.5 Social Media

We used Social Media to create and sustain awareness for the activities and results of 5G EVE among target audiences and all other interested parties. We decided to focus on particular Social Media channels to be most effective in reaching our target audiences.

6.2.5.1 Twitter

At the project start in July 2018, we set up a Twitter account under the name @5G_EVE (https://twitter.com/5g_eve – see Figure 8). It was used to redistribute news items published on the 5G EVE website and to connect with target audiences and anyone interested.

As of 22 June 2021, the 5G EVE Twitter account had **954 followers**.

6.2.5.2 YouTube

5G EVE set up a YouTube account in 2019 for sharing videos on its activities and results with its target audiences and other interested parties. We regularly published videos on YouTube, including interviews, technical demonstrations, and 2 professionally produced explainer videos.

6.2.5.3 LinkedIn

5G EVE is using the LinkedIn group of the 5G PPP to share information on events and activities the project partners are involved in.

In addition, a LinkedIn group for community building on topics related to 5G infrastructures is scheduled to be created in 2019 after project month 12. The group is specifically aimed at facilitating a productive dialogue with target audiences interested in using the 5G EVE end-to-end facility.

Figure 8: Social Media (Twitter)

6.3 Achievement of targets against key performance indicators

In order to measure the achievement of the communication and dissemination objectives outlined above, 5G EVE had defined a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) and target values for each KPI. 5G EVE achieved and often exceeded the target values for almost every KPI, as summarised in Table 19.

Table 19: Overview on communication and dissemination activities

#	Activity	Activity Type	Target Audiences	KPIs for Activity	Target Values Y1-3	Achieved Values Y1-3
1	Website	Publication	ALL	av. no. of visitors per month	200	312
				av. no. of doc downloads per month	50	42
2	Newsletter	Publication	ALL	no. of subscribers	120	207
3	Twitter	Publication	ALL	av. no. of posts per month	5	7
				no. of followers	200	954
4	YouTube	Publication	ALL	total no. of videos uploaded	12	29
				av. no. of viewers per video	100	66
6	LinkedIn	Publication	USE	av. no. of posts per month	4	0.5
7	Scientific papers	Publication	STD	av. no. of published papers p.a.	10	17
			5G3			
			UNI			
8	White papers and guidelines	Publication	USE	no. of published documents	4	6
			VER	av. no. of downloads per publication	100	48
			EIA			
			VCS			
			STD			
			GOV			

			5G4			
9	Press releases	Publication	PRE	no. of press releases	3	1
			ONL	no. of media coverage items	10	1
10	Flyers and brochures	Publication	ALL	no. of flyers and brochures to be produced	3	2
				Total no. of copies to be printed	2,000	400
				Total number of people to be reached via flyers/ brochures	2,000	400
11	Active presence at third-party events	Event	ALL	no. of presentations at third-party events	12	12
				no. of information & demo booths & stand	4	2
				av. no. of people reached per event	100	200
11	Workshops organised by 5G EVE	Event	USE	total no. of workshops to be organised	3	4
			VER	av. no. of participants per workshop	60	50
			SME	Total no. of workshop participants	180	200
			GOV			
			5G4			
			UNI			
12	Online events organised by 5G EVE	Event	USE	total no. of online events to be organised	12	13
			VER			
			SME	Total no. of participants	300	650
			GOV			
			5G4			
			UNI			

7 Impact beyond 5G EVE lifetime

As early mentioned in this deliverable, the standardization actions usually take long time, in some cases exceeding the lifetime of a project. Then it is important to plan sustainability of standardization actions further than the end of a given project. This is also the case of 5G EVE.

In some cases, the sustainability is achieved by the particular interests of the partners in the consortium. Since standardization actions are intrinsically aligned with partners' internal strategies, it is common that those industrial partners used to work on standardization fora continue pushing and supporting initiatives coming from ended projects.

Another way of given sustainability to the standardization actions is through the handover of such initiative to live projects where a common set of partners work. Thus, the token is passed to such other projects that provide the necessary continuity to the effort. This vehicle is easier for SMEs which are not usually involved on standardization matters.

In the case of 5G EVE a number of actions are yet a work in progress, and then continuity is expected beyond the end of the project.

The most relevant case is the ETSI INT [2] initiative. There the first WI on methodologies is close to be finished, but it is yet pending the launch of the second one on testing specifications. The ecosystem created around this effort, with the involvement of the three ICT-17 projects, guarantees an important basement on top of which keep in progress with the effort. The complementary ICT-19 projects together with projects from other calls but sharing the interest on vertical service validation ensures proper continuity and support, with the benefit of involving a very wide critical mass (from industrial partners to SMEs to academia).

Other cases, such as 3GPP [3], ORAN [14] or IETF/IRTF [5], has more industrial profile, and usually the actions there have continuity because of the involvement of specific industrial partners. This is also foreseen in the case of the outcomes derived from 5G EVE, in topics such as NPN for verticals or testing and benchmarking of different kind of technologies for the support of vertical services.

Last but not least, some other initiatives around the development of specific components or solutions, such in the case of ETSI OSM [11] or ETSI ENI [15], have a continuity since the progress produced in 5G EVE is provided in the form of reusable building blocks that permit augmentation or extension for future initiatives, so paving the way for new developments.

8 Conclusions

The 5G EVE project had a clear objective from the beginning in the wider purpose of impacting society and technology development at large. Two facets were had in mind in the inception of the project: to provide sufficient and impactful communication and dissemination of the project activities to help verticals to embrace 5G technologies by enabling simple and efficient experimentation; and to move into standardization for the different advances that could emerge from the project execution.

Generic dissemination has been crucial to engage verticals. Departing from the use cases initially defined in the project and complementing with new use cases during project execution (either internal to the project or external via ICT-19 initiatives), the project has promoted the adoption of 5G technologies through extensive experimentation, trying to reduce the gap in the adoption of verticals of novel 5G technologies.

Specific actions into standardization have contributed as well in this direction. Vertical services represent a promising business for the overall telecommunications industry, then it is extremely important to define standards ways of procedure for experimenting and validating services. This applies to multiple aspects such as testing and benchmarking methodologies, points of measurement, KPIs, etc. 5G EVE has contributed to create more stable and affordable environments in order to generalize the 5G adoption. The major result of this effort has been the creation of two specific WIs within ETSI INT [2] committee, being yet a work in progress.

Finally, consequence of the development of a new architectural framework, additional technology innovations have been developed in the project, most of them from participant SMEs. These novelties have been also transferred to the industry through contributions to SDOs.

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Annex: Assessment of Y1 Review with Respect to Standardisation Activities

During the Y1 review, a number of points were raised by the reviewers with regard to standardisation activities. The project took some corrective actions in order to address the comments received.

- *“In regard to Standardisation: Proceed with a new clustering for Y2, refocusing on the SDOs where more impact can be achieved (multisite orchestration and interaction within verticals).”*
 - The project took seriously this comment by focusing on those SDOs in which partners are most involved and in which specific 5G EVE components and developments can be positioned. This is reflected in the structure of the final cluster of targeted SDOs.
- *“The initial standardisation plan is very briefly described and missing concrete details”*
 - This was fixed by providing more detail in D6.2. This new deliverable D6.5 complements this fact with a more in deep view of the overall standardization activity in the project.
- *“The objectives of the project are still very relevant and ambitious. The project can – if successful – make a major contribution to supporting the introduction of 5G by providing access to testbeds with different types of network equipment. In particular, the attention to edge, already present (e.g. related to ETSI MEC specifications), has become increasingly relevant, since ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC41 IoT now incorporates edge computing in its Reference Architecture for IoT, and ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC42 AI is progressing in the same direction, as is the forward-looking ITU-T-FG-Net2030 group. A review of progress in those committees, beyond the ongoing attention to the 3GPP release process, may help guarantee that the project stays as 'future proof' as possible.”*
 - The project has taken also action on this comment by actively monitoring and contributing to 3GPP SA5 and ITU-T Network 2030. Regarding MEC, partners in the consortium supported the work item on MEC interconnection (now close to finish its first report), to facilitate integration of MEC capabilities in vertical-specific partners' private and public networks, as well as the support of the recent GSMA Operator Platform initiative, which also focuses on federating edge computing capabilities from different operators and providers. Despite partners of 5G EVE have been active in these two initiatives, the solutions proposed in the ETSI MC and GSMA initiatives have not been part of the project assets.

Other suggested groups, such as ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC41 and ISO/IEC-JTC1-SC42, were more difficult to target from the project because of the profile of the partners and the profile of the particular groups participating in 5G EVE. Then no other actions than monitoring were accomplished.
- *“The groundwork has been laid out – e.g. disjoint testing and validation tools were executed, and a set of initial testing and validation results were collected from use cases. An initial version of the KPI Performance Diagnosis framework has been designed, and the initial version of the KPI Performance Diagnosis framework has been designed. The work is properly documented to address the objectives set by the project, with the exception noted earlier in the assessment (Impact 1.): 'Objective 9 Innovation objective: Contribute to the relevant 5G standardisation fora' has not been demonstrated to have been addressed as 'contribute' in the current phase. The current phase seems to be 'receive only' as far as standards are concerned. New market opportunities are expected for vertical partners at a later stage in the project lifetime.”*
 - In line with the comment, the project has contributed to 3GPP for Rel.16, as well as in other fora for future capabilities relevant to 5G, such as intent-based mechanisms and the benchmarking of 5G technologies. In addition to that, the testing and validation framework has been extensively contributed to the ETSI INT initiative for vertical experimentation in 5G networks and beyond.